

Key trends for project management, a cornerstone for organizational success

Tendencias clave de la gestión de proyectos, pilar fundamental para el éxito organizacional

Arialys Hernández Nariño ^a

^a Universidad de Ciencias Médicas de Matanzas, Cuba, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0180-4866>,
arialishn.mtz@infomed.sld.cu

How to cite: Hernández Nariño, A. (2025). Key trends for project management, a cornerstone for organizational success. *Revista de Administración y Desarrollo de Proyectos*, 1(1), e202510.

Received: 19/02//2025, **Accepted:** 26/02/2025, **Published online:** 03/03/2025

In a world of rapid technological advances, project management has established itself as an essential discipline to ensure organizations' success, due to its impact on efficiency, innovation and organizational adaptability. Its development as a valuable field of study is manifested in the behavior of its scientific production and spheres of influence, which will be discussed below.

Scientific production: According to the search performed in the Scopus database (Figure 1), an increase is evidenced, characterized by a polynomial function with a confidence level of 47,53 %.

Figure 1. Research behavior on project management
 Source: own elaboration

analytics and business intelligence have also revolutionized decision making into an approach based on accurate data and reliable metrics. Tools such as dashboards and real-time reports enhance monitoring of project progress, with efficiency and transparency. Finally, operational excellence is consolidated through methodologies such as Lean management and Six Sigma, which seek to eliminate waste, optimize processes, reduce variability, ensure quality and continuous improvement in all operations.

These fields and their relationships align to bibliometric studies (Wulandari & Raharjo, 2023), which are increasingly consulted and addressed on a global scale. Sectors such as software industry make use of projects that foster innovation and efficiency in the creation of digital applications and platforms for the implementation of systems like enterprise resource planning (ERP) and customer relationship management (CRM). Construction and engineering are among the most studied and advanced business environments in the application of the aforementioned emerging tools (Zabala Vargas et al., 2023; Khan & Kwan, 2025).

An interesting point is that not only the need to develop projects constitutes the common aspect in health, education, public administration and energy sectors (Cruz Montero et al., 2020); but also the interconnection that is established between them.

In order to provide quality and affordable health care, technology, infrastructure and highly qualified human capital are needed, for whom research is central in the search for better treatments, effective drugs or more efficient and sustainable methods of managing health services.

Communications, manufacturing and energy are areas also adopting advanced technological approaches to improve their performance; they as well benefit from construction projects to optimize their spaces.

Ultimately, certification is of utmost importance for upgrading, validation of technical and practical skills, as well as the use of standardized methodologies such as PMBOK that are still highly valued (Cruz Montero et al., 2020).

This context reflects that the development and success of projects is conditioned by the fact that their management is increasingly based on adaptation to a complex and changing environment and, to this end, it must adopt approaches that promote effectiveness, flexibility and innovation as unavoidable premises.

Referencias bibliográficas

- Cruz Montero, J. M., Guevara Gómez, H. E., Flores Arocutipa, J. P. & Ledesma Cuadros, M. J. (2020). Áreas de conocimiento y fases clave en la gestión de proyectos: consideraciones teóricas. *Revista Venezolana de Gerencia*, 25(90), 680-692. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=29063559017>
- Khan, A. N. & Kwan, H. K. (2025). AI, Agility, and Environmental Performance: A New Framework for Construction. *Project Managers*, 151(3), 04025003. <https://doi.org/10.1061/JCEMD4.COENG-14584>
- Sedhom, I., Khodeir, L. M. & Fathy, F. (2024). Integrated agile facility management model for improving performance in construction projects. *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, 9(5), 171. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41062-024-01475-9>
- The Lens. (2025). CAMBIA. <https://www.lens.org/lens/search/scholar/analysis?q=%22Project%20management%22>
- Wulandari, H. & Raharjo, T. (2023). Systematic Literature and Expert Review of Agile Methodology Usage in Business Intelligence Projects. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Business Intelligence*, 9(2), 214-227. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jisebi.9.2.214-227>
- Zabala Vargas, S., Jaimes Quintanilla, M. & Jiménez Barrera, M. H. (2023). Big Data, Data Science, and Artificial Intelligence for Project Management in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction Industry: A Systematic Review. *Buildings*, 13(12). <https://doi.org/10.1061/JCEMD4.COENG-1458>

Editor: PhD. Yasniel Sánchez Suárez <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1095-1865>